

D2.2. Participation and impact report

Observing and Negating Matthew
Effects in Responsible Research and
Innovation Transition

D2.2 - Participation and Impact report
Version 1.0
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This deliverable presents an overview of the co-creation activities performed by the project. It draws on the input of all work packages.

ON-MERRIT - Grant Agreement 824612

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WP2 - Dissemination and Participation			
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Abbreviations

ON-MERRIT - Observing and Negating Matthew Effects in Responsible Research & Innovation Transition

OS - Open Science

RRI - Responsible Research and Innovation

SwafS (projects) - Science with and for Society

WP – Work Package

Executive summary

The document reports on the participatory methods and co-creation activities performed during ON-MERRIT, which constitute an integral element of the project. The co-creation activities in the project include participatory involvement in problem-formulation, methods design, and active co-construction of policy recommendations. This deliverable examines these activities, assesses stakeholder engagement and targeted engagement activities within ON-MERRIT and then summarises the outcomes of ON-MERRIT Task T2.3 (“Co-creation activities”) and provides an update on Task 2.4 (“Final validation workshop”, to take place in February 2022).

The co-creation activities took place in every work package with different implementations, depending on the research needs; from community feedback to expert engagement to surveys and workshops, each of these activities aimed to verify and confirm that the research was solid and aligned with best practices.

Despite the promising premises, however, the co-creation instrument proved to need careful planning and strong links with the communities we intended to engage with to ensure adequate participation. Nonetheless, the co-creation experience so far proved to be a useful tool that might be employed even beyond the SwafS projects, as a method to check the validity, on a regular basis, of research and project findings and recommendations with the stakeholders, who will be the recipients of those suggestions.

1. Introduction: Participatory approaches within ON-MERRIT

ON-MERRIT¹ is a 30-month project funded by the European Commission under the SwafS (Science with and for Society)² programme to investigate how and if open and responsible research practices could worsen existing inequalities. Our multidisciplinary team uses qualitative and computational methods in order to examine advantages and disadvantages in Open Science and Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) across academia, industry, and policy. ON-MERRIT aims at eventually suggesting a set of evidence-based recommendations for science policies, indicators and incentives, which could address and mitigate cumulative (dis)advantages, so-called Matthew effects.

An integral element of ON-MERRIT is the use of participatory methods of co-creation. Our project aims to contribute to optimising equity in the transition to Open Science and RRI. Seeking to investigate and explain mechanisms affecting equity within these areas means that our research methods necessarily have involved input from researchers, industry professionals and policy-makers through a wealth of surveys, interviews and focus groups. However, since the ways in which levels of equity may be defined differently amongst our various stakeholder groups, as well as across regions, disciplines and demographics, ON-MERRIT also has sought maximal stakeholder-input in the design of the research itself. With this primary research phase complete, and as ON-MERRIT enters its final phase of synthesis of findings and formulation of recommendations, this stakeholder input becomes even more central. Distilling our findings, evaluating their importance, and producing recommendations for action in response, are all areas where the involvement of stakeholders is crucial. Co-creation is the narrative thread of many projects funded under the EC SwafS programme as a way to build suggestions and best practices with the help of the stakeholders targeted by those recommendations.

To these ends, ON-MERRIT has employed a range of co-creation methods including participatory involvement in problem-formulation, methods design, and active co-construction of policy recommendations. This deliverable takes stock of these activities, assessing stakeholder engagement and targeted engagement activities within ON-MERRIT and thus summarising the outcomes of ON-MERRIT

¹ <https://on-merrit.eu/>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/science-and-society>

Task T2.3 (“Co-creation activities”) and providing an update on Task 2.4 (“Final validation workshop”, to take place in February 2022).

The report is structured as follows: Chapter 2 discusses co-creation activities within each work package; Chapter 3 reports on lessons learned by providing an assessment of the success (or otherwise) of these co-creation activities undertaken in ON-MERRIT and draws some conclusions on the co-creation experience in the project.

2. Activities

In this section we describe the co-creation activities undertaken within each project Work Package.

2.1 Work Package 2: Dissemination and participation

ON-MERRIT Work Package (henceforth WP) 2 “Dissemination and participation” ensures the project’s liaison, engagement and alignment with all relevant stakeholders and communities from research, industry, policy-making and civil society from the selected disciplinary areas. It leads participatory processes to engage stakeholders in the co-creation of research instruments and analyses, as well as fostering awareness about the project in domains of interest and facilitating the uptake of project results, specifically with respect to co-creation activities within each Work Package, reported below.

In addition, WP2 has been responsible for general outreach and communication with stakeholders, which has set the basis for such engagement by increasing awareness of the project. This has been achieved through multiple lines of action, including:

- **Engagement with the SwafS community:** From the start of the project, RRI and OS communities have been invited to provide feedback through the ON-MERRIT Twitter page as well as the RRI Ecosystem Facebook page. Further, the National Experts on Open Science (NOADS) identified by OpenAIRE maintain close relationships with their national policymakers and have been invited to comment and make suggestions as well. In addition, ON-MERRIT participates in several initiatives to help the project keep pace with the latest developments around co-creation in the European landscape. These are, in particular, the CoRRI forum³ and the SwafS Ecosystem, launched respectively by the SISCODE and the SuperMORRI project⁴. The CoRRI forum, in particular, promotes the wide application of RRI in co-creation activities for practitioners, co-creation labs and other initiatives. ON-MERRIT also takes part in the Cross-SwafS Stakeholder Forum for Responsible OS led by the ROSiE project⁵, whose aim is to co-create novel practical tools to foster a responsible Open Science and Citizen Science.

³ <https://siscodeproject.eu/article/corri-forum-promotes-the-second-cycle-of-workshops-co-creation-journeys-of-the-siscode-labs/>

⁴ <https://super-morri.eu/rri-ecosystem/>

⁵ <https://rosie-project.eu/>

- **Social media:** ON-MERRIT curates a Twitter account with close to 400 followers to engage communities and run information campaigns: one was about the project deliverables⁶ published in 2020, with tweets explaining the relevance of our research findings to the wider research community; the following campaign was related to the webinar series described below. Another campaign will take place to publicise the deliverables published in October 2021, complemented by blog posts describing the research outcomes in detail. In addition to the campaigns, the Twitter channel promotes readings and useful resources about Open Science and RRI, such as the blog post “Open Science: who is left behind?” published on the LSE blog⁷.
- **Webinars:** A webinar series⁸ ran from May until July 2021 with four webinars, overall attended by around 100 participants. They were recorded and have over 200 views on YouTube⁹. The webinars covered Matthew Effects in Science, Bibliometrics, the Matthew effect and diversity in academia, Open Science as a driver to change, and Open Science in Indonesia. The webinars aimed to present the project objectives and results and explored wider issues related to RRI and Open Science with experts in those fields. We wanted to stress ON-MERRIT related topics, including research assessment, ways for RRI to change career progression and equal evaluation, Open Science as a driver of changes in research practices, and practices in Open Science in the Global South. Doodle polls were used to engage with the community and to attract participants to join the webinars.
- **Presentations:** Since its inception, the project has been showcased in several events with posters and presentations reporting on the project results. In particular:
 - SUPER MoRRI annual event, Leiden 29/01/2020;
 - EASST/4S 2020, virtual 19/08/2020;
 - RefResh 2020, virtual 06/10/2020;
 - Citizen Science SDG Conference, virtual 13/10/2021;
 - STS Graz 2021, virtual 04/05/2021;
 - New HoRRizon final conference, virtual 26/05/2021;
 - Open Science Fair, 21 and 22/09/2021.

The blog post “Perspectives on Open Science and Inequity: Who is left behind?”¹⁰ was initially conceived as a panel at the Open Science Conference 2020 which was cancelled due to the onset

⁶ <https://on-merrit.eu/results/>

⁷ <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2020/10/23/open-science-who-is-left-behind/>

⁸ <https://on-merrit.eu/news/2021-04-20-on-merrit-webinars/>

⁹ <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC6NDpswfKaINOWvC1skWTWg>

¹⁰ <https://on-merrit.eu/news/2020-03-12-panel-osconf2020/>

of the COVID-19 pandemic. Members of the consortium were invited to give presentations about ON-MERRIT and related topics in other closed meetings, e.g. with the Swiss National Science Foundation.

- **Final event:** To take place in early 2022, the ON-MERRIT final event will provide an additional venue for discussion and validation of the project results. The theme of the final event will revolve around equity in research and publishing practices that could foster or prevent that equity.

2.2 Work Package 3: Research cultures, support and incentives

WP3 “Research cultures, support and incentives” aimed at identifying and measuring the extent of Matthew Effects in science, and if and how they are influenced by the application of RRI and Open Science principles. WP3 produced the “RRI and Open Science dataset¹¹”, the significance of which lies in its potential to answer questions that are key to understanding what motivates academics with respect to their research practices and publishing behaviours. It also produced a large-scale quantitative study about cumulative advantage in Open Science and RRI¹² to identify, measure and assess the effects of cumulative advantage in Open Science and RRI with a focus on the creation of research outputs within academia. For both outputs, a dissemination campaign was run via Twitter to collect feedback on the research findings and to inform the public about the next research steps which were summarized in the study on the “Uptake of Open Science and Responsible Research and Innovation in Policy and Training¹³”. A final round of feedback will be conducted in due course with the OS and RRI communities following the publication of a series of blog posts, each dedicated to summarising the results of the research activities and findings in the project as a way to validate the results.

2.3 Work Package 4: Innovation and Industry

WP4 “Innovation and Industry” aimed at investigating the levels of uptake of Open Science resources and RRI in industry. To complement the desk research, it adopted co-creation activities in Task 4.2, “Readiness to exploit Open Science resources amongst economic actors”. In that task, several interviews with stakeholders from SMEs and industries were conducted; the interviews had the goal of understanding information-seeking behaviours, awareness of Open Science in general and the uptake of Open Science Resources, such as Open Access, Open Data and Open Source specifically, as well as the general capacities for Open Science uptake. After that, based on the feedback received from the interviewees, a questionnaire was created and circulated among the interviewees as well as the ON-MERRIT consortium

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3874586>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5547286>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5604632>

to solicit further feedback. In addition, the RRI Ecosystem Facebook and LinkedIn pages were used to attract participants to the study, as well as the dissemination via the project's Twitter channel. The questionnaire was then distributed to selected SMEs in the domains of agriculture, climate and health. The results of this research are described in D4.2: Drivers and barriers to uptake of Open Science resources in industry¹⁴.

2.4 Work Package 5: Policy-making and societal actors

WP5 "Policy-making and societal actors" investigated the role of Open Access and Open Science resources in policy-making, to understand the extent of Matthew Effects within policy-making and public participation and provide evidence to mitigate these effects. In WP5, co-creation activities were employed in two ways. To begin with, a large international survey was conducted among policy-makers in Task 5.2 "Information-seeking behaviours amongst policy-makers in the age of Open Science". After an internal review phase by project partners and external experts¹⁵, a co-creation method was developed to gather feedback on an initial version of the survey questions. There, a pdf version of the survey instrument was made available via Zenodo¹⁶. Information about the survey structure and content was disseminated via the ON-MERRIT and the RRI Ecosystem social media channels along with a link to a feedback form in order to seek broader stakeholder feedback on the instrument's design. Zenodo recorded 81 views and 42 downloads, which suggests some interest in the survey; unfortunately, no specific feedback on the survey content was received. The survey was nonetheless carried out and results are described in a dedicated deliverable¹⁷.

Task 5.3 "Mapping participation in RRI and policy making" also relied heavily on co-creation methods that were employed following three expert workshops, each of them themed for one of the ON-MERRIT case-study disciplines (climate change, health and agriculture). Experts and policy-active researchers were invited to these workshops to share their experience regarding participatory processes, to identify barriers to participation, and to reflect on experts' experiences with facilitating policy-making through their research, including which stakeholders and civil society actors were or were not heard, and for which reasons¹⁸. In addition to discussing their personal experience with participatory approaches involving multiple stakeholders, these policy-active experts were invited to reflect specifically on the role of OS and RRI in fostering equitable participation in and access to research and policy-making. Based on participant

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5549761>

¹⁵ The external experts involved in the survey check belong to the OpenAIRE NOADs <https://www.openaire.eu/contact-noads>.

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4452787>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5507619>

¹⁸ The results of this research are described in detail in D5.3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5550533>.

feedback received during the data collection phase (pre-workshop interviews and expert workshops), an additional two-hour online co-creation workshop was held (unplanned as per the project proposal) to validate preliminary findings after completing the data collection phase. All workshop participants were invited to attend, but only a small number (five out of eighteen) followed the invitation. We presented our preliminary findings and then asked participants to respond to them in a breakout session where they were able to compile their feedback using an online collaboration tool¹⁹. Their feedback was then analysed in a closing group discussion in greater detail. Though participation was limited, we found this to be a very fruitful exercise as new topics of concern emerged that had not been present in our data, and participants helped us to co-create several promising recommendations²⁰.

The activities described above have also been summarized in a blog post published on the ON-MERRIT website²¹.

2.5 Work Package 6: Synthesis, validation and policy recommendations

WP6 “Synthesis, validation and policy recommendation” is responsible for bringing together the various strands of research in the project to synthesise knowledge of the extent of the threats posed by Matthew Effects in relation to current RRI and OS policy interventions. At the time of writing this deliverable, several other co-creation activities are taking place in relation to WP6. In particular, work on T6.2 “Scenario modelling of interventions to overcome Matthew Effects in RRI and Open Science transition” has recently started. Although there are not many activities yet, initial ideas for the model were presented at summer schools on the methodology of agent-based modelling with the aim of gathering feedback from participants that could potentially help to further extend the model.

The other WP6 co-creation activity concerns T6.4 “Guidelines and policy recommendations”, with the explicit objective to produce recommendations and guidelines based on the findings of the project’s research activities (all completed in September 2021). Therefore, three co-creation workshops with stakeholders (researchers, research funders and policymakers, research managers) have been developed to test the validity of our findings around implementing open research practices. The workshops are taking place in November 2021, at the time of this report, with the aim of co-creating recommendations for the development of Open Science policies. Each workshop aims to include around ten participants from European institutions and beyond, representing a diversity of research areas, academic ages and professional backgrounds, to provide feedback and comments on the recommendations developed by the

¹⁹ For the results of the feedback activity, see <https://ideaboardz.com/for/Initial%20Feedback/3886035>.

²⁰ <https://miro.com/app/board/o9JlEg5MjA=/>

²¹ <https://on-merrit.eu/news/2021-07-19-co-creation-checkpoint/>

ON-MERRIT research work packages. Workshop participants have been selected, in part, from the experts that were involved in the WP5 workshops who agreed to participate in further ON-MERRIT activities, as well as select members of the project's Advisory Board²² and other experts, whose input and experience was judged to be potentially beneficial for the project.

In terms of organizing these co-creation workshops, all participants received a pre-workshop survey containing general information about ON-MERRIT's aims, the key problem areas and approaches, as well as asking for feedback and recommendations based on the project's findings for three target audiences: research-performing institutions, science policy-makers/funders, and researchers. We use the same set of questions across the three stakeholder workshops, inviting feedback on recommendations targeted at the three stakeholder groups introduced above, from representatives of each stakeholder group. More specifically, each workshop is devoted to gathering feedback from representatives of one stakeholder group on the entire set of recommendations in the hopes of soliciting a wide range of suggestions to help target the final list of recommendations to fit the respective audiences. Additionally, in the pre-workshop survey, one task for participants was to come up with original recommendations based on condensed versions of research results. These recommendations will likewise feed into the final recommendations produced by the ON-MERRIT consortium, helping us to produce solid and useful guidelines that could support the development of equitable Open Science practices.

²² <https://on-merrit.eu/about/advisory-board/>
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3. Discussion and conclusions

Co-creation is an essential part of ON-MERRIT, as demonstrated by the activities detailed in this report. Co-creation represents a powerful asset to projects that seek validation and confirmation of their outcomes. ON-MERRIT made use of co-creation for engaging with stakeholders during different project phases, to ensure alignment of our research with best practices and to keep relevant stakeholders informed.

Nonetheless, especially given the extraordinary circumstances of the COVID-19 pandemic (the effects of which have been felt throughout most of the project's run-time), these activities have not always run smoothly and it is worth reflecting on these difficulties to learn lessons for the future.

The COVID-19 pandemic significantly affected stakeholder engagement within the project. Firstly, pandemic travel restrictions meant the team did not have the opportunity to engage in face-to-face dissemination activities, potentially to the detriment of further networking possibilities. More importantly, though, many ON-MERRIT research activities had foreseen face-to-face engagement with research participants, including interviews (WP3, 4, 5), workshops (WP5) and on-site contextual inquiry (WP4), which all had to be moved online due to restrictions on travel and gathering during 2020/2021. The project team worked hard to minimise disruption to project activities by moving these activities online. This was for the most part very successful although the timelines of two deliverable reports had to be extended due to difficulties in participant recruitment. In the end, all research activities were completed within the scope originally foreseen. Utilising online environments for these activities was not all negative, however. Innovative tools such as the collaboration platform Miro²³ were used to aid discussion and facilitate engagement with participants, for example.

Another challenging aspect was reaching out to the target groups with which ON-MERRIT wished to engage to gather feedback. Challenges arose either because of a lack of direct contacts among the stakeholder groups, because the stakeholders did not understand the purpose of the request, or because they felt they could not effectively contribute to the task. That aspect also ties in with an issue we experienced when trying to create community engagement; in fact, when discussing relevant but abstract issues like the ones ON-MERRIT deals with, it was not always straightforward for the community to understand the point we were trying to make. By contrast, engagement was more successful when

²³ <https://miro.com/>
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participants in the discussions around ON-MERRIT topics had some previous knowledge of the project and a clear understanding of the expectations from their participation and feedback.

However, using co-creation methods showed the need for careful planning of activities, with a clear structure, objectives and a certain understanding of the community that is intended as the main stakeholder of the action. Taking the case of Work Package 4 as an example where the community link was not very strong overall, in fact, some difficulties arose when engaging with the stakeholders to get their opinion and feedback which resulted in a somewhat limited research sample.

Nonetheless, the co-creation experience so far proved to be a crucial tool to check the validity, on a regular basis, of research and project findings and recommendations with the stakeholders, who will be the recipients of those suggestions.